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Fast report for clinicians

Understanding the overarching pathomechanism in Oshtoran Syndrome (H63D Syndrome type 3)

To understand the pathomechanism in Oshtoran Syndrome, particularly given its complexity and the involvement of multiple systemic and cellular dysfunctions, it is crucial to integrate knowledge from various domains, including immunology, neuroendocrinology, and mitochondrial biology.

Initial Trigger

PANDAS (Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections) acts as one of several initial triggers. The autoimmune response to streptococcal infection causes neuroinflammation, that activates a cascade of immune and metabolic dysregulation.

This autoimmune attack on the basal ganglia and associated structures leads to neuroinflammation, which disrupts normal neurological and autonomic functions. This process can easily cause long-term alterations in the brain's regulatory mechanisms. The initial immune response primes the immune system to be hyper-reactive, causing subsequent exaggerated responses to various stimuli.^{1,3,9}

Activation of H63D Mutation

The H63D mutation in the HFE gene is associated with iron dysregulation. When activated, this mutation can lead to non-transferrin bound iron

(NTBI) accumulation, which causes oxidative stress and damages various cellular structures, in a similar way that copper does to patients suffering from Wilson's disease.

Excess NTBI catalyzes the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative stress and cellular damage, particularly affecting mitochondria. Mitochondrial damage results from oxidative damage, impairing the cell's ability to produce energy efficiently through oxidative phosphorylation, leading to a shift towards anaerobic glycolysis and lactate production.^{18, 19,21}

Mitochondrial Dysfunction: PDH-Cytopathy

The diagnosis of PDH-cytopathy points to a specific mitochondrial dysfunction involving the pyruvate dehydrogenase complex, crucial for the conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA in the citric acid cycle. PDH-cytopathy limits the cell's ability to fully utilize glucose through oxidative phosphorylation, forcing reliance on less efficient anaerobic pathways, resulting in increased lactate production and metabolic stress. Mitochondrial dysfunction affects multiple organ systems, contributing to the systemic nature of the symptoms observed in Oshtoran Syndrome.^{8,9,24,25}

Chronic Immune Dysregulation

The immune system's chronic dysregulation contributes significantly to the ongoing pathology in Oshtoran Syndrome. Type 4 Reactions are key. These delayed-type hypersensitivity reactions exacerbate inflammation and tissue damage, affecting multiple organs. Persistent low-grade inflammation further impairs cellular and mitochondrial functions, creating a vicious cycle of damage and dysfunction.

Neuroendocrine and Autonomic Dysregulation

The interplay between the central nervous system (CNS) and the endocrine system (HPA axis) plays a critical role in maintaining homeostasis. In Oshtoran Syndrome, this balance is disrupted.

Frequent episodes of excessive catecholamine release (e.g., adrenaline) indicate severe autonomic dysregulation. These storms can exacerbate metabolic instability and stress responses. A HPA

Axis Dysregulation is seen often in patients with H63D Syndrome type 3 (Oshtoran Syndrome). Keeping the HPA axis stable is a key factor in Oshtoran Syndrome because otherwise adrenal insufficiency or dysregulation, which affects stress responses and metabolic stability does not work as it should.

Conclusion

The overarching pathomechanism in Oshtoran Syndrome involves a complex interplay of autoimmune, genetic, metabolic, and neuroendocrine factors. Understanding this interplay helps in comprehending the systemic and multifaceted nature of the disease. While the initial autoimmune response from PANDAS acted as the trigger, the activation of the H63D mutation and subsequent mitochondrial dysfunction compounded the problem, leading to a chronic state of immune dysregulation and neuroendocrine instability.

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